

Spectrophotometric Determination of Cobalt with Rubeanic Acid in Presence of Quinoline, α -Picoline and Collidine

M. B. SAHA and A. K. CHAKRABURTTY

Department of Inorganic and Analytical Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-700 092

Manuscript received 28 December 1981, revised 11 May 1982, accepted 28 September 1982

Cobalt has been estimated with rubeanic acid in combination with quinoline or collidine at 390 nm and with α -picoline at 410 nm from the yellow colour developed in aqueous alcoholic medium. Beer's law is obeyed within the range of 0.58 ppm to 3.5 ppm of Co(II) with RA and quinoline and 0.5 ppm to 4 ppm of Co(II) with RA and α -picoline or collidine. Optimum pH range has been found to be 7 to 8.1. The respective sensitivities are 0.0042 $\mu\text{g Co/cm}^2$, 0.0041 $\mu\text{g Co/cm}^2$ and 0.0034 $\mu\text{g Co/cm}^2$ for RA and quinoline, RA and α -picoline and RA and collidine. Effect of diverse ions, composition of the complexes in solution and optimum working range have been studied.

THE enhancement of colour and solubility of the cobalt complex of rubeanic acid in the presence of pyridine and piperidine facilitating thereby the spectrophotometric determination of cobalt has been reported^{1,2}. In the present communication, the spectrophotometric determination of cobalt with rubeanic acid (RA) in presence of quinoline, α -picoline or collidine is described. The molar extinction co-efficient in all the three cases is distinctly higher than the corresponding rubeanic acid-pyridine and rubeanic acid-piperidine systems.

The yellow colour developed by the three systems mentioned above has been spectrophotometrically studied separately. The systems absorb maximally at 390 nm in case of RA and quinoline, at 410 nm in case of RA and α -picoline and at 390 nm in case RA and collidine. The optimum pH range has been found to be 7 to 8.1 in each of the systems where Beer's law is obeyed. The respective sensitivities for RA+quinoline, RA+ α -picoline and RA+collidine are 0.0042 $\mu\text{g Co/cm}^2$, 0.0041 $\mu\text{g Co/cm}^2$ and 0.0034 $\mu\text{g Co/cm}^2$. The corresponding molar extinction coefficients are 13560, 14060 and 14190, respectively.

The results of the detailed spectrophotometric studies including the effect of diverse ions, study of the composition of the complexes, Ringbom's plot, Beer's law, effect of pH and order of addition of reagents are presented in this paper.

Experimental

Chemicals, reagents and apparatus: Standard cobalt solution was prepared by dissolving cobalt nitrate and the cobalt content of the solution was determined by BPHA³. A 0.1% solution of rubeanic acid was prepared in 95% ethanol. This solution was stable for several days. 10% solutions of freshly

distilled quinoline, α -picoline or collidine in distilled alcohol were used for all determinations. Solutions of other cations and anions were obtained from analytical grade reagents. A Hilger-Vispek spectrophotometer and an Elico-Model L1-10 pH meter, were used for absorbance measurements and pH determinations, respectively.

Absorbance curve: The yellow coloured solutions developed with the addition of 1 ml of 0.1% rubeanic acid solution and varying amounts of the three different bases (4 ml in case of quinoline, 3 ml in case of α -picoline and 0.5 ml in case of collidine) to cobalt(II) solution showed maximum absorbance at 390 nm when the base ligand was quinoline or collidine and at 410 nm when it was α -picoline.

Effect of pH, reagent and time: Effect of pH was studied with Co(II) solutions containing 1.4 $\mu\text{g Co/ml}$, 1 ml rubeanic acid and varying amounts of the heterocyclic bases in a final volume of 25 ml. The measurements were made in aqueous alcoholic medium. The optimum pH remained in alkaline region between 7 to 8.1.

1 ml of 0.1% (w/v) solution of rubeanic acid was found to be sufficient for an amount of cobalt within the range 3.75 to 4 ppm for any of the three bases. Higher reagent concentration had no effect on the optical density of the solution.

The colour was not stable for a long time but the absorbance could be measured safely within one and a half hour of preparation of solutions.

Concentration of quinoline, α -picoline, collidine and alcohol: 4 ml quinoline, 3 ml α -picoline or 0.5 ml of collidine (10% solution of each in distilled alcohol) was found to be sufficient to keep the complex in 90% aqueous ethanol. The bases were added after the addition of the reagent solution.

Procedure : To a slightly acidic solution of cobalt, free from interfering ions, was added 1 ml of rubeanic acid solution (0.1% w/v) followed by the addition of 4 ml quinoline, 3 ml α -picoline or 0.5 ml collidine for the three respective methods of estimation. The final volume in each case was made up to 10 ml with distilled alcohol. The absorbance measurements were made at the respective regions of maximum absorption for the bases.

Beer's law and optimum range : The cobalt rubeanic acid quinoline system was found to obey Beer's law over the ranges 0.58-3.5 ppm of Co(II). The optimum working range from Ringbom's curve was ascertained as 1.17 ppm to 3.5 ppm of Co(II). The rubeanic acid α -picoline system and the rubeanic acid collidine system for the determination of Co(II) gave identical results, both in the cases of Beer's law and optimum working range. Beer's law and optimum working range for the above two systems are within the ranges 0.5 ppm to 4 ppm and 1.17 ppm to 4 ppm of Co(II), respectively.

Molar extinction coefficient and sensitivity : The mixed ligand complex depicts a marked rise in molar extinction coefficient and sensitivity over those of the individual complexes with rubeanic acid or aromatic base. The molar extinction coefficient and consequently the sensitivity is found to be maximum when the base ligand happens to be collidine followed by α -picoline, quinoline, piperidine and pyridine in decreasing order. This order finds a correlation with the basicity of the ligands which also follows the same decreasing order in case of collidine, α -picoline, quinoline and pyridine but differs for piperidine. The results are shown in Table 1.

Composition of the complexes : The study of the complexes in solution by Job's method of continued variation⁴ and molar ratio method⁵ shows a uniform cobalt : rubeanic acid ratio of 2 : 3 in all the mixed ligand systems. This is in conformity with the compositions arrived at by Ray and Ray for the same reagent with cobalt⁷. From the high pH in which the complex is formed,

TABLE 1

Metal ion	Reagents	Sensitivity	Molar extinction coefficient
Co ²⁺	Rubeanic acid and pyridine	0.0050 μ g Co/cm ²	11300 ^a
Co ²⁺	Rubeanic acid and piperidine	0.0048 μ g Co/cm ²	12590 ^a
Co ²⁺	Rubeanic acid and quinoline	0.0042 μ g Co/cm ²	13560
Co ²⁺	Rubeanic acid and α -picoline	0.0041 μ g Co/cm ²	14060
Co ²⁺	Rubeanic acid and collidine	0.0034 μ g Co/cm ²	14190

it is surmised that cobalt in the soluble complex is in the +3 state which finds corroboration from similar observations made in the case of cobalt hydroxamic acid complexes⁸.

Effect of diverse ions : The tolerance limits for foreign ions for 2.3 ppm cobalt(II) in each case are acetate 50 ppm, oxalate 100 ppm, tartrate and citrate 300 ppm. Molybdate, tungstate and vanadate can be tolerated up to 400 ppm. Phosphate and EDTA interfered. The interferences due to silver and nickel ions could be eliminated with thiourea and KCN solutions, respectively. Cu²⁺, Bi³⁺, Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, Hg₂²⁺, Hg²⁺, Pd²⁺ and Cr³⁺ interfere even when present in small amounts.

References

1. J. XAVIER and P. RAY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **35**, 435.
2. M. B. SAHA and A. K. CHAKRABURTTY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 1137.
3. S. K. SINHA and S. C. SHOME, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1959, **459**, 21.
4. P. JOB, *Compt. rend.*, 1925, **180**, 928; *Ann. Chim. (Paris)*, 1928, **9**, 113.
5. A. E. HARVEY, JR. and D. L. MANNING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 448.
6. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", 3rd Edn., Interscience, New York, 1958.
7. P. RAY and R. M. RAY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **4**, 118.
8. A. K. CHAKRABURTTY, Proceedings of the Symposium on the Chemistry of Coordination Compound, Agra, 1959 Part III, p. 235.